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MODERN DIMENSIONS

in **EUROPEAN EDUCATION**

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PROCEEDINGS

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О ПИСМЕНОСТЪ**

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IN
THE EUROPEAN EDUCATIONAL
AND
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И
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IN
THE EUROPEAN EDUCATIONAL
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A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF SOME OF THE MORE SIGNIFICANT MOMENTS IN BULGARIAN-ITALIAN POLITICAL AND KULTURAL RELATIONS

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Abstract: *Bulgarian-Italian relations date back to the period of antiquity, passed through the Middle Ages, and reached the new and most recent times. During all these years, several contacts were built, which were reflected in political, cultural, and public life. This article provides a brief overview of some of the more significant moments in the bilateral relationship. Examples are indicated that had an impact on the development of contacts. Emphasis is placed on diplomatic relations, as well as cultural ties between Bulgarians and Italians from the end of the 19th and the first half of the 20th century.*

Keywords: *Bulgarian-Italian relations, Bulgaria, Italy*

Relations between Bulgarians and Italians date back centuries. Over the years, depending on the situation in different eras and specific situations, contacts have ranged from sporadic to saturated and extremely intense. We find the first information about contacts noted for the beginning of the 6th century. In books V–VIII of the „History of Justinian's wars with Persians, Vandals and Goths“ Procopius of Caesarea notes that Hun mercenaries were often present on the lands of the Apennines. It is assumed that this is how he marked some of the proto-Bulgarian tribes that came to this region at that time. Bulgarian mercenaries were also part of the Byzantine army. The same author informs us that they landed in Calabria (Bruzio) with the help of the Byzantine fleet. Similar invasions were noticed in subsequent years. Apart from Procopius, other chroniclers also write about this. Among them we can name Comes Marcellinus and Pope Gregory the Great. They aim at the Bulgarian presence indirectly. They perceive it as part of the presence in the Apennines of various tribes, collectively referred to as „Huni“. [1] With their name „Bulgarians“ (Vulgares) are certain representatives of the proto-Bulgarians who settled in the middle of the 6th century on the territory of the former Longobard kingdom. This happened during the time of their king Alboin (565–572). A century later, in the period 663–668, as noted by the Byzantine chroniclers Theophanes the Confessor and Patriarch Nicephorus, some of the Proto-Bulgarian tribes led by Khan Asparukh's brother – Khan Altsek (Altsiok) settled in the lands of part of today's Campobasso district to Benevento. In “History of the Lombards”, Pavel Deacon, describing these years, states that the duke of the Bulgarians (Vulgarumdux) Alceco, settled in the lands of the Lombards, which were ruled by King Grimoald (662–671) [1]. Gradually they moved south from Rome. In fact, from then on they were referred to by the name „Bulgarians“ (Vulgares), which was continuously used for them in the following years. This is what the Frankish chronicler Fredegar wrote about the same events in his work “Gesta Dagoberti I regis Francorum”: “At that time the Bulgarian governor named Alceco, who had left his people for an unknown reason, peacefully reached Italy and went with all his army to King Grimwald, promising him that he would serve him and live in his kingdom. Grimwald, sending him to his son Romwald in Beneventum, ordered the latter to fix the abodes of Alceco with his people. Romwald received him favorably, and assigned them scattered places of settlement, which until then had been deserted, namely: Sepinum, Bovianum et Iserniam, and in other towns in his territory, and Alceco himself, changing the name of his dignity, commanded instead of a chief (voivode, dux) to be called gastaldius, i.e., ruler.” These words give reason to assume that it was the Bulgarians led by Altsek who settled in the lands of today's Italy. Alcek himself received the title “gastald” (gastaldo) and became the governor of an

administrative district. Bulgarians also settled in Central Italy – in Sepino, Boyano and Isernia, part of the Molise region. This is reported by various chroniclers. Nowadays, their words are confirmed by the results obtained during the excavations of individual necropolises. Such were made near the town of Campochiaro, where graves with soldiers laid in them were discovered. They were buried together with their horses, as well as with all the battle gear belonging to them. The conclusion is that in Sikkim they are descendants of proto-Bulgarians who settled here in the 7th century. In 1987 in the area of Vicene and Morione, between Boiano and Sepino in southern Italy, a total of 120 graves were discovered and studied during excavations. It is characteristic of them that the bodies were laid with an eastern orientation. Stirrups, arrows, spears, skeletons of whole horses were found. It shows they are here buried soldiers. In some of the graves there are many objects. A ring was found in one of them, which is supposed to have been in the possession of Altzek himself or his successor. Burials of women were also discovered, in which amber and other objects were found. All this gives reason to conclude that there is a transfer of culture from the Carpathian region to this place. The conviction remains that these are graves of proto-Bulgarian families and their descendants. All this is convincingly confirmed by Italian historians. For them, the presence of Bulgarians in these lands is indisputable. Many modern historians confirm the conclusion already made in the 40s of the XX century by Prof. Vincenzo D'Amico, that more than 700 settlements in the Apennines were founded by proto-Bulgarians, and a large part of them still retain the self-awareness of their origin. To this day, in some towns of the province of Salerno, the local population proudly calls themselves „descendants of Bulgarians“.

During the Middle Ages, diplomatic and commercial relations were established between the Bulgarian state and some of the Italian cities (so-called free cities), as well as separate kingdoms on the territory of Lombardy, Central and Southern Italy. Italian merchants passed through Bulgarian lands and enjoyed certain privileges. There are active connections with the major commercial and cultural centers of Venice and Genoa. In fact, Italians know Bulgarians well. Many descendants of the proto-Bulgarians remain living in the Apennines. They retain their self-awareness and call themselves Bulgarians. As such, they are also accepted by the local population. Their presence becomes permanent, and this is marked by the preserved names characteristic of the local toponymy. In various documents there are names of settlements that have a Bulgarian character – for example the village of Celle di Bulgeria (translated as “Bulgarian cells”). Mountain hills have similar names – Monte Bulgaria Mountain. In the life of St. Nil Young – a source from the 10th century, written by his student Bartholomew, an incident with the saint is noted, in which the “Bulgarian monk” is mentioned. All this shows that Bulgarians were known in Italian settlements during this period as well. In some years, intensive contacts were also made between the Bulgarian rulers and the papal institution. For a certain period, Bulgaria even concluded a union with the Roman Catholic Church, which was carried out under certain conditions. The presence of the Bulgarians remains permanent. During the Middle Ages, the Bulgarian state made active contacts not only with merchants and representatives of cities from Northern and Central Italy, but also with those from the most extreme parts of the Apennines – Sicily. In fact, relations with them date back to the end of the 10th century and the beginning of the 11th century. During this period, Sicily was under the rule of the Normans. Then, as in the following years, these lands emerged as an important cultural and commercial center in the Mediterranean, where different ethnic and cultural groups met. Bulgaria and Sicily are also connected by sea trade. Sicily was an important trading partner, from where traders imported fruits, spices, and textiles. At the same time, Bulgarian products such as honey and wine are popular in Sicily.

Almost all contacts between Bulgarians and Italians were interrupted after the inclusion of the Bulgarian lands in the boundaries of the Ottoman Empire in the last years of the 14th century. This continued for a rather long period of time. A new reach was observed only from the end of the 18th century. They were marked by contacts between individual Bulgarian and Italian merchants, which were the result of their trips. During the period of the Bulgarian Renaissance, representatives of the nascent Bulgarian intelligentsia had direct contact with Italian culture. Bulgarians visit

several cities on the Apennines, the most common of which are: Rome, Venice, Genoa, Florence, and Milan. What was seen there, and the new knowledge gained had a significant impact on the emerging Bulgarian Renaissance intellectuals. Many Bulgarian educators and scientists undergo training in Italy. There is data that Paisius of Hilendar spent some time in Italian cities, where he became acquainted with the study of Italian culture and education. Grigor Parlichev studied in Milan and brought the Italian experience in education. The principles laid down in the language reform that Vasil Aprilov is imposing in Bulgarian schools are based on Italian experience. In the following years, the theme „Italy“ was prominently present in the work of Lyuben Karavelov, Petko R. Slaveikov, as well as the journalism of Hristo Botev [2]. And the Italian political model, which is based on the struggle of individual Italian regions for unification, has been formed since the beginning of the 19th century. The vision of a unified Italy of Giuseppe Garibaldi had a strong influence on the Bulgarian actors. About 15 Bulgarians joined the Italian national liberation movement organized by him in the period 1860–1871. Among them is the famous captain Petko Voivoda. At the suggestion of the latter, a group of Garibaldians was created, which included Italians and Bulgarians. It actively participated in the battles during The Cretan Uprising of 1867. Garibaldi's view of the methods to be used in the struggle for Italian national liberation and unification is followed with interest by the ideologist of the Bulgarian national revolution, Georgi Rakovski. He follows the actions of Garibaldians with attention and subjects them to analysis. The result of this can be seen in the program documents of the Bulgarian national liberation movement developed by him, which bear a strong resemblance to the statutory documents of the Italian Carbonari of those years. Another prominent Bulgarian, who actively worked to shape program documents and a comprehensive vision of how the struggles of the Bulgarians should proceed – Ivan Kasabov, was also influenced by Garibaldi's ideas. What's more: He assisted in the realization of a meeting in London between Bulgarian officials led by Teofan Rainov and Mazzini – Garibaldi's first assistant. During this meeting, the Italians expressed strong support for the Bulgarian cause, even declaring the readiness of the Garibaldians to support the Bulgarian efforts, including with squads, at the moment when the Bulgarians revolted against the Ottoman Empire. Not only Bulgarians are interested in Garibaldi. As a result of his contacts with Bulgarian actors, he also showed interest in their activities. Information about this is provided by one of his letters sent in October 1876 to the members of the Bulgarian Revolutionary Central Committee (БРЦК) in Bucharest. It reads: “My dear friends, the Italian people have for your people a sympathy deserved by their misfortunes and their heroism. I grieve that I cannot personally participate in your battles. I wish you perseverance in your bright mission. Yours, Giuseppe Garibaldi” [3]. Italy played an active role in supporting the Bulgarian struggle for independence in the 1960s and 1970s. Italian diplomats and politicians, such as Carlo Felice, openly advocated the view that the Bulgarians should be helped and that the Bulgarian people should be given autonomy, like their neighbors – Greeks, Serbs and Romanians, who have received with the Edirne Peace Treaty of 1828. In 1864, the first Italian consulate was opened in Varna. Four years later – in 1868, such a consulate was also opened in Ruschuk (Ruse), and since 1875 there has been a consulate in Sofia as well. The consul in Sofia – Vittorio Positano – is particularly well-known in the Bulgarian consciousness. In the last phases of the Russo-Turkish War, at the end of 1877, as doyen of the consuls accredited in Sofia, he convinced most of his colleagues to oppose the demand of the commander of the Turkish troops, Osman Pasha, to leave the city. In this way, the intention of the Turkish command to burn the city before the arrival of the Russian troops was thwarted. He actively protects the Bulgarian population together with the consuls of France and Austria-Hungary. It is little known that even before him similar actions were carried out by the Italian consul in Ruschuk – Enrico De Gubernatis. He turned out to be the only consul in the city who did not leave it and thus contributed to the Danube city not being destroyed by the retreating Turkish troops. Also, he convinces the local commandant not to encroach on the civilian population [4], [5].

After the restoration of Bulgarian statehood, an Italian diplomatic agency – the Consular Commission for Bulgaria – was opened in Sofia. Domenico Brunenghi was appointed first consul

general on November 10, 1878. On July 3, 1879, he presented himself officially to the Bulgarian Prince Alexander I Battenberg, and on July 25, his credentials as the official Italian representative in Bulgaria were deposited. In this way, Italy, along with 10 other European countries – Austria-Hungary, Belgium, Great Britain, Prussia, Russia, the Netherlands, France, Romania, and Serbia, established regular diplomatic relations with the Principality of Bulgaria. Until the end of the 19th century, the diplomats who headed the Italian mission in Sofia were: Renato De Martino, Carlo Alberto Gerbè de Sonà, Alessandro Riva, Giulio Silvestrelli. In 1903, Bulgaria also opened its diplomatic representation in Rome. The first manager of the Bulgarian diplomatic agency was Dimitar Minchovich. At the time of the important year for Bulgaria, 1908, when independence was proclaimed, a representative with the rank of diplomatic agent and consul general in Sofia was Fausto Kuki Boaso. He actively works to strengthen bilateral relations. As a result, in 1909, the status and rank of the Bulgarian diplomatic mission in Rome and the Italian one in Sofia were changed. They rise to the rank of Legations. The diplomats of the two countries – Dimitar Rizov and Fausto Kuki Boaso – become special envoys and are entitled “ministers plenipotentiary”. Diplomatic relations remained in this form until 1943, when changes occurred in Italy related to the establishment of the Italian Republic. After the end of the Second World War – in 1945, bilateral relations were again regulated. Diplomatic missions in both capitals are actively working. Since 1964, the Bulgarian and Italian legations have been elevated to the rank of Embassy and their heads have been accredited as ambassadors extraordinary and plenipotentiary – in Sofia and Rome, respectively.

Apart from the diplomatic aspect, the bilateral Bulgarian-Italian contacts in the sphere of culture, science, and public relations, activated since the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, are also important. Cultural ties that have their roots since the Middle Ages are developing in the new conditions. Many Bulgarians start to study and work in Italy. Dozens of Bulgarians go to the Italian cultural centers: Florence, Turin, Milan, Venice, Naples, who study at universities and various schools. There are also contacts between Bulgarian and Italian artists – artists, architects, representatives of various fields of arts. This leaves a significant mark on the formation of their ideas about the development of Bulgarian culture and society. Among the Bulgarians who feel a strong influence of the Italian masters can be mentioned: Ivan Marinov, Boris Georgiev, Nikolay Dylgerov. Since the end of the 1980s, several Italians have shown interest in Bulgaria. Luigi Bolongaro and Giorgio Cannella became painting teachers at the Varna State Boys' High School. In the boys' high school in Plovdiv, Caesar Drog became a teacher. All three remain interesting drawings related to their stay in Bulgaria and their meetings with the Bulgarians [6]. From the beginning of the 20th century, there were also the first translations of Italian fiction into Bulgarian. Works by Italian authors such as Luigi Pirandello, Giovanni Boccaccio, etc. are translated. Konstantin Velichkov, Veselin Hanchev, Vasil Stefanov are among the first translators from Italian to Bulgarian. Ivan Vazov translated for the first time into Bulgarian the works of Dante Alighieri, including “The Divine Comedy”. These translations play an important role in familiarizing the Bulgarian public with Italian literature. Pencho Slaveykov also made an important contribution to strengthening Bulgarian-Italian contacts in the field of literature. He resides many times in Italy. His numerous visits had a strong influence on his work. During his visits to various Italian cities, he had the opportunity to get to know Italian culture, literature, and history in detail, which is also reflected in his poetic works. It is strongly influenced by the beauty of Italian nature and historical monuments. His admiration for Italy and its culture is evident in works such as Italian Scenes and Italian Night [2]. In addition to literature, a strong influence is also exerted in the field of architecture. In fact, it dates to the middle of the 19th century, when many Bulgarians began to actively visit Italian cities. Among other activities, they brought the ideas of an architectural arrangement that began to be introduced in the larger urban centers. During the construction of numerous new public buildings, which began in the 1980s, buildings were built in Sofia, Plovdiv and Varna that reveal the strong influence of Italian architecture. Italians make their own project, for which they are hired by the local municipal authorities. This process became particularly active from the beginning of the 20th century. Felice

Varinini came especially to Bulgaria and supported the projects of several buildings in the capital Sofia. In 1912, Giuseppe Buoni made the project of the so-called Mendeleev High School in Sofia, also known as the Italian High School. Ricardo Marino designed the Ministry of War building.

An important element of Bulgarian-Italian relations in 1930 was the wedding of the Bulgarian monarch Tsar Boris III with the Italian princess Giovanna (Joanna) of Savoy, who became the Bulgarian queen. The wedding is part of Bulgaria's political strategy aimed at strengthening the ties of the Bulgarian state with other European countries. Italy is considered a key partner in this context. The wedding is also a skillful diplomatic move, which aims to highlight the good neighborly relations between Bulgaria and Italy and to strengthen the cooperation between the two countries both in the diplomatic aspect, as well as in the economic and social aspects.

After the end of the Second World War, Bulgaria fell into the sphere of defined socialist countries. The formation of the so-called The Iron Curtain and the resulting international relations led to a certain narrowing and cooling of relations between Bulgaria and Italy. One of the reasons for this is communist tendencies that dominate Bulgarian foreign policy. After this period and the collapse of the socialist camp in 1989, the relations between the two countries became significantly more active. I am actively working on strengthening economic and political cooperation. The accession of Bulgaria to NATO in 2004 and to the European Union in 2007. Also contributes to closer relations between the two countries as they seek to work together within the framework of the European and Atlantic communities. Commercial, cultural, and political relations between Bulgaria and Italy are developing in a positive direction and continue to be important for the societies and economies of both countries.

Conclusion

Over the years, the relations between Bulgaria and Italy have been marked by various moments that left an imprint on state relations, political and economic contacts, and the cultural sphere. In a historical aspect, the two countries share a common historical and cultural connection, which starts from the period of the Roman Empire, then of Byzantium and goes through the entire Middle Ages. There was development in the periods of the Crusades, as well as the relationship with the Papal Curia. Throughout the years, these contacts have contributed not only to political but also to the development of commercial and cultural ties. There is mutual influence. In modern times, direct diplomatic relations between the two countries have been established since the end of 1878. They contribute to the promotion of exchanges between the two countries.

Today, Bulgarian-Italian relations are good and characterized by intensive cooperation in various fields.

– In economic terms, Italy is one of Bulgaria's important trade partners in the European Union. Trade between the two countries is significant, with Italian investments in Bulgaria playing an important role in the country's economic development.

– In the political aspect, Bulgaria and Italy cooperate within the framework of the European Union and NATO, supporting the development of common values and interests. Political relations between the two countries are characterized by dialogue and cooperation on issues of common interest, such as security, migration, and economic development.

– Cultural and educational ties have marked a marked rise over the years. Italy is known for its rich culture and history, which makes the country an attractive partner for cultural exchange and development of common activities in the field of cultural heritage preservation and its presentation to the people. There is active cooperation in the field of science and technology, and the sharing of scientific knowledge and innovation is of mutual interest to both countries. Student exchange, cultural projects, and cooperation in the field of education are also important aspects of the relationship between the two countries.

All the above reveals that Bulgarian-Italian relations, not only over the years, but also today, are characterized by partnership and cooperation in various fields and continue to be important for the politics, economy, and societies of both countries.

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КРАТЪК ОБЗОР НА НЯКОИ ОТ ПО-ЗНАЧИМИТЕ МОМЕНТИ В БЪЛГАРО-ИТАЛИАНСКИТЕ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИ И КУЛТУРНИ ОТНОШЕНИЯ

Резюме: *Българо-италианските отношения датират още от периода на Античността, преминават през средните векове и достигат до ново и най-ново време. През всичките тези години се изграждат редица контакти, които намират отражение в политическия, културен и обществен живот. Настоящата статия прави кратък обзор на някои от по-значимите моменти в двустранните отношения. Посочват се примери оказали влияние върху развитието на контактите. Акцент се поставя върху дипломатическите отношения, както и културните връзки между българи и италианци от края на XIX и първата половина на XX в.*

Ключови думи: *българо-италиански отношения, България, Италия*

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